

The Analysis of Collaboration of the Environmental Department in Preparation of Strategic Environmental Study of Detailed Spatial Plan (Ses Dsp) in Karangasem Regency

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ABSTRACT: The preparation of the Strategic Environmental Study of the Detailed Spatial Plan (SES DSP) is crucial to be implemented and is an obligation for the local government. The preparation of the SES DSP is an effort to realize sustainable development because currently there is widespread misuse of space utilization in Karangasem Regency such as development on the coastal border, conversion of agricultural land, and land use by illegal mining entrepreneurs. This shows the need for a review of the SES DSP preparation process carried out by the preparation team, through this study the author aims to observe the collaboration of each actor involved in the SES DSP preparation process by reviewing it using the Collaborative Governance theory and the concept of sustainable Strategic Environmental Study. So that the findings of this study are in the form of actor collaboration strategies in implementing the preparation of the SES DSP in Karangasem Regency. The research method used in this study is qualitative research with a grounded theory approach. The results of this study show that the Environmental Department Collaboration in the preparation of the SES DSP has carried out 3 stages of collaboration starting from the obstacle identification stage, the debate strategy stage, and planning collaborative actions. There are six obstacles in the collaborative process of preparing the SES DSP in Karangasem Regency, namely the quality of human resources, budget resources, natural resources, data, community interests, and land conversion.

KEYWORDS: Collaboration, Environmental Department, SES DSP

I. INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian government is currently intensively carrying out development to realize equitable development in Indonesia, with the principle of sustainable development. Sustainable development is often referred to as SDGs, following data on the implementation of SDGs in Indonesia from 2019-2023, where Indonesia is ranked 75th in the world, while at the national level based on a report from the Ministry of National Development Planning/Indonesian Ministry of National Development Planning, the achievement of National SDGs in 2023 showed that 76% of SDGs indicators had been achieved. The report on the achievement of SDGs in Indonesia is shown in the graph below:

Graph 1.1 The Level and Index Score of Indonesian SDGs

Source: Bappenas, 2023

The determination of the SDGs index value is based on the achievement of SDGs indicators, there are 17 goals, 169 targets, and 289 indicators. These indicators are coordinated in four pillars, namely Social Development, Economic Development,

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Environmental Development, and Legal and Governance Development. The implementation of the 4 pillars of the SDGs in Indonesia has not yet fully achieved the SDGs indicators, as can be seen from the image below:

Figure 1.1 Achievement of Indonesian SDGs Target in 2023

Source: Bappenas, 2023

Based on the above figure, of the four pillars of the SDGs, the environmental pillar shows the highest level of unattainability, which is 70%, while only 25% has been achieved. This shows that attention to environmental conservation in Indonesia is still low. To overcome this problem, the Indonesian government has a very important role, including the Regional Government has an important role in realizing sustainable development (SDGs) in the environmental sector. Sustainable development policies are regulated in Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 11 of 2022 concerning the Implementation of Achieving Sustainable Development Goals. To realize sustainable development, the government needs to carry out good spatial and regional planning that supports the achievement of the principles of sustainable development, which is followed up by the Regulation of the Minister of Agrarian Affairs and Spatial Planning/Head of the National Land Agency of the Republic of Indonesia No. 5 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Integrating Strategic Environmental Studies (SES) in the Preparation of Spatial Plans, which is stated in Article 3 paragraph 1 stating that the central government and regional governments are required to make SES to ensure that the principles of sustainable development have become the basis and are integrated in the development of a region through the preparation of Spatial Plans (SP).

The Bali Provincial Government through the Department of Public Works, Spatial Planning, Housing and Residential Areas (tarubali, 2023) stated that the preparation of the Detailed Spatial Plan (DSP) is very important to optimize the use of space in the Province, the benefits of the DSP are to fill the gap in the Regional Spatial Planning (RSP), the DSP allows for more effective control of space use, the DSP as a guide in granting permits, detailing the general plan, the DSP can be an instrument to encourage environmentally friendly sustainable development, the DSP helps in planning infrastructure development and the depth of content and map specifications compared to the RSP. The initial stage in preparing the DSP is by preparing the SES. Karangasem Regency is one of the regencies in Bali in realizing environmental development guided by the SES DSP, in accordance with the results of the author's initial observations through several literature that Karangasem Regency still experiences problems related to space utilization, these problems are such as:

1. Development problems in the coastal border area in Karangasem Regency that are not following the zone. There is the construction of resorts or tourist cottages in the coastal border area, even jutting out into the sea, thus hampering the activities of fishermen and the community (N.K.S, 2021)
2. The problem of the construction of the Resort in the Bukit Gumang Temple Area is not following the Karangasem Spatial Planning Regulation No. 17 of 2020 (Atnews, 2023).
3. The problem of land use experts for rice fields in Karangasem Regency is still rampant, as many as 445.34 hectares of rice fields in Karangasem Regency are threatened with being converted into buildings. (Wayan, 2023)
4. The problem of land use by unlicensed or illegal mining entrepreneurs in Karangasem Regency is still rampant, there are 90 mining entrepreneurs but only 48 businesses have business permits. (KompasTV, 2023)

Problems related to the use of space in Karangasem Regency indicate that the preparation of the SES DSP is not yet optimal because there are still many violations and overlapping spatial planning regulations related to the determination of zones that have an impact on environmental damage in Karangasem Regency. The Karangasem Regency Government formed an SES DSP preparation team in 2023 through the Decree of the Regent of Karangasem No. 9/HK/2023 concerning the Working Group for the Strategic Environmental Study of the Karangasem Regency Detailed Spatial Plan. The SES DSP working group is not only from government circles but also includes NGOs (Non-Governmental Organizations) concerned with the environment in Karangasem Regency. Based

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on the explanation of the problems above, the researcher is interested in raising the research title, namely “The Analysis of Collaboration of Environmental Department in Preparation of Strategic Environmental Study of Detailed Spatial Plan (SES DSP) in Karangasem Regency”

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative research method with a grounded theory approach. According to Taylor (Murdiyanto, 2020) qualitative research methods are research procedures that produce descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observed behavior. Meanwhile, grounded theory according to Martin and Tuner (Ayu & Budiasih, n.d, 2014) is a research method that seeks to develop hidden theories behind the data where this data is collected and analyzed systematically. The grounded theory approach is used in this study to find new strategies for implementing the collaborative process of compiling the SES DSP in the Karangasem Regency.

Data analysis techniques according to Bogdan (Sobari, 2020) are the process of systematically searching for and compiling data obtained from interviews, field notes, and other materials, data analysis can be done by organizing data, breaking it down into units, synthesizing, arranging into patterns, choosing which ones are important and which ones will be studied and making conclusions. In this study, researchers carried out two stages of data analysis, namely data analysis before going into the field and data analysis during going into the field. Data analysis before going into the field by analyzing data from preliminary studies or secondary data that will be the focus of the research, then researchers conducted data analysis going into the field by collecting field data, reducing data, or sorting and selecting important data according to the focus of the research. The final stage is presenting the results of data analysis.

III. DISCUSSION

The Process of Collaboration of the Environmental Department in Drafting SES DSP in Karangasem Regency

The preparation of SES DSP (Strategic Environmental Assessment of Detailed Spatial and Regional Planning) in Karangasem Regency is the authority of the Karangasem Regency Environmental Department in collaboration with the SES DSP working group consisting of RAO (Regional Apparatus Organizations), academics and the private sector. The SES DSP document is an important document that must be designed before carrying out development, through this document the development zones that will be included in the Karangasem Regency RSP will be determined. Based on the results of research analyzed using NVIVO and disrupted at three stages in the collaboration process, the following results were obtained:

Diagram 1. The Pattern of Task Force Collaboration of SES DSP in Karangasem Regency

Source: the result of data analysis, 2024

The diagram above shows that the collaborative process of compiling the SES DSP in the Regency consists of several stages, namely identifying obstacles, determining opportunities, planning collaborative actions (determining planning and determining long-term plans), and determining debate strategies (dialogue phase).

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Tree Maps 1. The Process of Drafting Collaboration of SES DSP

The above matrix shows that of the three stages of collaboration that have been running well, namely the debate strategy and identification of obstacles. However, the next stage after identifying obstacles, namely determining the solution to the obstacles has not been implemented properly and actor participation is still very minimal, and the stage of planning collaborative actions has not been implemented properly. There are several types of obstacles to the collaboration of the SES DSP working group shown in the diagram below:

Diagram 2. Obstacles to Drafting Collaboration of SES DSP in Karangasem Regency

Source: the result of data analysis, 2024

Diagram 2 shows that there are six types of barriers to collaboration in the preparation of SES DSP in Karangasem Regency, namely budget resources, Natural Resources, Human Resources quality, community interests, data, and land conversion. The second stage in the collaboration process for preparing SES DSP by the working group is to carry out a debate strategy where at this stage there is a dialogue phase between the actors involved in the SES working group. Based on the results of interviews with informants, namely the Karangasem Regency Environmental Department, the Karangasem Regency Disaster Management Agency, Bebandem Sub-district Head, Manggis Sub-district Head, and Kubu Sub-district Head, almost all of them stated that they were involved or participated in the SES DSP preparation process, but only the Manggis Sub-district Head did not participate in the SES DSP preparation process even though he had been appointed as the SES working group in the Decree of the Regent of Karangasem No. 9/HK/2023 Concerning the Strategic Environmental Study Working Group for the Detailed Spatial Plan of Karangasem Regency (2). The form of discussion applied in the process of preparing the SES DSP by the Environmental Department and the working group, namely through public consultation, FGD, Socialization, and Meetings, can be seen in the tree maps below:

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Tree Maps 2. Form of the Discussion of SES DSP Draft in Karangasem Regency

Source: the result of data analysis, 2024

Based on the above tree maps, the four dominant forms of discussion carried out by the Environmental Department of Karangasem Regency are public consultation and FGD. Public consultation is an important stage to involve the community in the process of preparing the SES, this process aims to obtain input, suggestions, and responses from the wider community regarding the spatial plans to be prepared. This shows that the SES DSP working group has carried out its duties and responsibilities in accordance with the Regent's Decree to carry out public consultations related to the preparation of the SES DSP in Karangasem Regency. While FGD is a discussion method that involves small groups, in FGD the topics discussed are focused on specific issues that require further study. Each form of discussion above is interrelated and supports each other. The process of preparing the SES DSP requires active involvement from various parties, including the community, stakeholders, and the government. In addition, these various forms of discussion also reflect the principles of sustainable development which require openness, accountability, and public participation in the spatial planning and management process.

The Implementation of Sustainable Value of SES DSP in Karangasem Regency

The SES DSP is a study aimed at realizing sustainable development, 3 sustainability values need to be considered in making the SES DSP, (3). Based on the results of the analysis, a comparison was obtained regarding the application of the SES DSP sustainability values which are shown in the tree maps below:

Tree Maps. 3 The Value of SES Sustainability

Source: the result of data analysis, 2024

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In accordance with the above matrix, it shows that the SES DSP of Karangasem Regency has realized the value of relevance which includes the relevance between regions, the relevance between sectors, and the relevance between stakeholders, in addition to the relevance value, the SES DSP has realized the value of balance, especially the value of the balance of utilization with protection. Where in the development process, the Karangasem Regency government has paid attention to environmental preservation by implementing the value of justice, namely carrying out control over the management of natural resources. So the SES DSP in Karangasem Regency has implemented 3 SES sustainability values.

The Model of Sustainable Collaboration in Preparing SES DSP in Karangasem Regency

The findings of this study based on the results of data processing found a sustainable collaboration model in the preparation of SES DSP in Karangasem Regency as shown in the diagram below:

Diagram 3. The Model of Sustainable Collaboration

The ongoing collaboration in the preparation of the SES DSP involves several important phases, and the dialogue phase is one of them. In this phase, the participation of actors from various sectors, stakeholders, and regions is key. Here are some important points related to this collaboration:

1. Inter-Sectoral Linkages: Actors from various sectors, such as environment, economy, and social, need to work together to understand the cross-sectoral impacts of the DSP. Each sector has different perspectives and data that are important for a comprehensive analysis.
2. Inter-Stakeholder Linkages: Stakeholders such as local governments, communities, and the private sector need to be involved. They provide input, identify problems, and help formulate better solutions based on their experiences and needs.
3. Inter-Regional Linkages: Problems and solutions often involve multiple regions. Inter-regional collaboration helps ensure that planning not only solves local problems but also considers broader impacts.

Information and Data Exchange For an effective SES DSP process, the exchange of relevant information and data between the actors is essential. This helps ensure that all parties have a common understanding of the problem and the proposed solutions. Each actor may face unique challenges according to their context. Ongoing dialogue helps in identifying and addressing these issues effectively. This collaboration must be supported by good communication mechanisms, openness, and commitment from all parties so that the SES DSP process can run smoothly and produce quality and sustainable planning.

IV. CONCLUSION

Collaboration of the Environmental Department in the Preparation of SES DSP with the working group has gone well where almost all working groups are involved in the process of identifying obstacles, there are 6 obstacles in the collaborative process of preparing SES DSP. The dominant form of discussion is carried out by the Environmental Department, namely public consultation and FGD. SES DSP Karangasem Regency has reflected 3 sustainability values.

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